

LINGUISTIC AND COGNITIVE ANALYSIS OF CHILDREN'S GAME NAMES

Matmusayeva Muhayo Azamovna

Teacher of Ferghana State
university faculty of pedagogy
and psychology

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10669055>

Abstract

The article discusses the importance of games and toys in the development of children's oral speech in preschool education.

Key words

Pupil, toy, doll, upbringing, education, fairy tale, speech development, preschool education, writing, national toys, national values.

The study of the emergence and development of a child's speech is relevant not only from the point of view of psychology, but also of personal and social significance. Speech is a structural element in the content of communicative activity, which, in turn, plays a decisive role in the development of the child's cognitive activity. Through communication and speech, the child learns to obtain information from the treasury of the socio-historical experience of mankind. The development of oral monological speech in preschool age provides the basis for successful teaching at school.

One of the main game tasks for the development of the speech of a preschool child is the enrichment of the child's words, in mastering concepts, in understanding the polysemy of the words used and their semantic shades. In games, speech activity develops, interest and attention to the native language is brought up. The game is an activity aimed at the correct upbringing of a child in all respects. The game develops man as a harmonious generation. The toy is a kind of object of this thing, it will find out the purpose of the child and will help to direct it to this goal. Many research scientists have proven that through toys, children fall into situations that they face in the future and are taught how to get out of them.

By getting to know the child toys, playing, they get to know the world around them. Children want to have a relationship between themselves, cultures of treatment for each other, to talk among themselves as if they were adults. Through toys, the child will be able to explain what he wants to tell you, those around him. They enrich their knowledge of being through toys.

L. about the theory of the game and the role of toys in the development of the child's personality. S.Vygotsky, A.N.Leontiev, D.B.Elconins conducted effective

research. Great Russian scientist A. M. Gorky said that " the Toy, first of all, impresses the child, and this feeling is the beginning of understanding." The toy introduces the child to the environment, teaches them, strengthens their impressions and satisfies the need for communication.

The toy is of great importance in the period from the birth of a child to the age of 3 years. Because they motivate themselves during the playing, learn the rules of the laws of organizing a game: with a doll they play as mother and daughter, with a rocket or a flywheel, with an airplane they begin to play the role of a driver. Through toys, the game is able to explain in what way it is going and what the goal is. The child delivers the feelings inside to the parents through play. The child forms his creative activity, knowing that the content of the game depends on the toy. By playing toys, the child forms his world and shares new ideas, and we must help develop these ideas.

Toys have the strongest educational effect for children, because everything is represented by a variety. Animals, plants, transports, various tools, various shapes, even a person himself is told to the toy as dolls. Toys the first life in the life of a child forms visions and gradually develops slowly. The child enters that environment playing a toy. As an example, a child tries to help patients by talking to himself as a doctor while playing a doctor doll.

As the child grows up, he begins to sort out toys. They are self-beneficiaries or playtime choose a toy based on what the child wants.

The toy develops and forms the child in every possible way, speech, memory, emotions, thinking. N.K.Krupskaya wrote that "Toys are of great importance for introducing children to the real world around them, for the development of their emotions."

There are different classifications for toys, which are divided into: didactic toy, educational games, theater game, sports game and musical games.

Didactic toys-in the process of playing teach children about their lifestyle, nature, various phenomena. Deepens children's knowledge. Didactic games pay great attention to the development of children's speech.

Educational play-teaches children education through play. In this, along with the game, knowledge, qualifications are acquired. Theater play – in modern theater, the term "play" is used by the actor to convey to the user through various means of expression-speech, facial expressions, gestures, various actions.

Sports game-action games aimed at keeping children healthy. Children are refreshed, cheerful, Carthaginian throughout the day through sports

games. Musical play-children form their interest in music through this game. Develops musical abilities. This game gives children joyful and cheerful moments. Our national traditions are also formed through games in children. Children need to explain each game.

Toys take a big place in the life of a child until he goes to school. Children try to play all the toys when they are young. He later begins sorting toys as he gets older. What they need at the same time is communicated to those around them through toys. In preschool organizations, toys are played to a small group of children (3-4 years old) who are mainly intended to play freely by hand. Tight, pointed toys cannot play toys that are dangerous for a child's life. In the middle group (4-5 years old), children are slightly more complex than in the small group. In it, children can perform roles with the tutor through toys. Through the roles he performs, speech also develops in the child. New words learn. Defects in pronunciation are also gradually corrected. A large group (5-6 years old) of children will be able to freely play toys on their own. Roles are played through various games and toys, taking place among themselves. The preparatory group (6-7 years old) children can now easily choose toys.

The difference between the game and the toy is that through the game, children themselves learn to adapt differently to different environments. The play involves the children themselves. In the game, the psyche of children, we can know what is going on in their fantasies. Through the game, speech, treatment of children develops. Toys attract children with their colorfulness. Each child plays different toys. Depending on what kind of toy the child is playing, it is possible to find out his inner world. The attitude towards the child in his family also indicates that the child is playing toys.

Dolls are toys that depict a human figure. Dolls are made for almost all girls, most of all, boys. Through the doll, children form an opinion about various professions in themselves and play themselves selectively by choice of dolls based on their interests. Someone is in the role of a mother, another is in the role of a daughter, and another is a doctor, etc. In infancy, the child receives a spiritual influence from what kind of toy oshno catches. Dolls form qualities in children such as beauty, elegance, fearlessness. The doll first came to Uzbekistan 150 years ago, a doll named "Barbie" from the United States of America.

Since foreign dolls were far from our nationality, their children from an early age tried to imitate adults, thinking as if they were adults. After independence, the creation of a national puppet is created in every possible way to create conditions for our entrepreneurs so that we do not forget about our nationality,

and also bring nationalism to the next generation. The demand for national dolls in our country is increasing day by day. Through these dolls, children learn our national heritage, our traditions.

The development of a child's speech is an important and complex process. The main period of speech development is associated with the period of gaming activity. Accordingly, training will be more effective if conducted in the form of a game. There is usually no need to insist on operating in the form of a game, since in fact any game is of great interest to children.

The influence of the toy on the development of the child's speech is great. In the games that he spends every day with toys, the child learns to name not only the objects that he uses, but also their characteristics, sizes, shape, color, etc. He adds the toys to the game in accordance with his ideas and determines their relationship with the rest.

Socialize through the objects and individuals involved in the game. The child leads all his actions in the game along with speech.

In speech cultivation classes, children can be organized in the game "find and describe" with the aim of forming descriptive, observational and cognitive abilities. To organize this game, different toys are selected: two dolls - one with a bow and the other without a bow; two cats of different colors. Toys are viewed and compared one by one; by saying their characteristic features and differences, the child's vocabulary wealth is activated. The Governess then hides the toys (so that the children can quickly find them) and offers to find them: "the Saint finds a white kitten, The Princess a black, and the Nigora a doll with a bow". Children find and bring toys, the teacher's questions ("What kind of cat do you have? What's on the cat's head? And what is it?") The child names and describes them with the help of a caregiver.

As a result of this conversation, opinions were summarized based on the different responses of the children: "the Queen found a black kitten. He has ears on his head, large eyes, a mustache. The kitten also has a long tail. "Children are asked to repeat the educator's description if they learn to answer questions well and correctly. Thus, observation, consideration, question and answer, conversation, analysis-synthesis methods are used here, aimed at helping the child to describe the topic.

The use of toys as a means of developing the child's oral speech and enriching his vocabulary will have a quick effect. The toy makes it possible to strengthen and activate the vocabulary in the child, serves as a source of new words. The

toy evokes only positive emotions, a desire to speak in a child. The child's knowledge increases through his interest in representation and storytelling.

References:

1. Djalalova, N. (2023). PIANO PERFORMANCE AS A FACTOR THAT ACTIVATES STUDENTS' MUSICAL AND AESTHETIC WORLD VIEWS AND DEVELOPS MUSICAL CULTURE. *Science and innovation*, 2(B4), 339-342.
2. Ataboeva, S., Kholikova, G., Jalalova, N., & Shoxista, U. (2021). STYLISTIC PROBLEMS OF COMPOSER S. RAKHMANINOV IN PIANO CONCERTS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(05), 104-108.
3. Yelena, V., Nigora, D., & Margubahon, V. (2022). THE ROLE OF FOLK ART IN RAISING THE MORALE OF YOUNG PEOPLE. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(3), 699-702.
4. Raxmonaliyevna, A. G. Z. (2021). System of Vocation and higher Education in Germany. *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, 7(12), 316-318.
5. Ergashevna, T. L. (2023). OF CHILDREN THROUGH THE ART OF MUSIC SPIRITUAL, AESTHETIC AND MORAL TASTE QUALITIES EXPLAIN THE CONTENT AND FIND. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(4).
6. Mirzayeva, G. F., Jabbarov, O. O., Tursunova, L. D., & Buvamukhamedova, N. T. (2021). GOUTY NEPHROPATHY: DIAGNOSIS, TREATMENT APPROACHES. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(11), 503-509.
7. Матмусаева, М. А. (2017). Оилада болаларни меҳнатга ўргатиш. *Молодой ученый*, (4-2), 23-24.
8. Матмусаева, М. А. (2019). ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧУВСТВА РОДИНЫ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ НА ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНЫХ И ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЯХ. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (3-4), 103-106.
9. Матмусаева, М. А. (2016). ТАЛАБАЛАР ПОРТФОЛИОЛАРИНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШ ШАРОИТЛАРИ. In *Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера* (No. 9, pp. 129-131). Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
10. Матмусаева, М. А. (2016). ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ЎҚУВ ФАОЛИЯТЛАРИНИ НАЗОРАТ ҚИЛИШНИНГ ИННОВАЦИОН ХАРАКТЕРИ. In *Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера* (No. 9, pp. 127-128). Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
11. Махамдалиевна, Y. D., & Matmusaeva, M. (2021). On Lingvofolcloristic Units. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 11, 169-171.

12. Матмусаева, М. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАСИ-МАКТАБГАЧА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАР ИЖТИМОЙ ТАРБИЯ МАСКАНИ. ИЎДКОР О'ҚИТУВЧИ, 2(20), 130-132.
13. Matmusayeva, M. A., & Rustamova, N. A. (2021). DEVELOPING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. Theoretical & Applied Science, (6), 658-660.
14. Azamovna, M. M. PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN.
15. Матмусаева, М. А. (2017). Оилада болаларни меҳнатга ўргатиш. Молодой ученый, (4-2), 23-24.
16. Матмусаева, М. А. (2019). ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧУВСТВА РОДИНЫ В ВОСПИТАНИИ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ НА ВОСПИТАТЕЛЬНЫХ И ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЯХ. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, (3-4), 103-106.
17. Матмусаева, М. А. (2016). ТАЛАБАЛАР ПОРТФОЛИОЛАРИНИ ТАЙЁРЛАШ ШАРОИТЛАРИ. In Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера (No. 9, pp. 129-131). Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
18. Матмусаева, М. А. (2016). ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ ЎҚУВ ФАОЛИЯТЛАРИНИ НАЗОРАТ ҚИЛИШНИНГ ИННОВАЦИОН ХАРАКТЕРИ. In Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера (No. 9, pp. 127-128). Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro.
19. Махамдалиевна, Y. D., & Matmusayeva, M. (2021). On Lingvofolcloristic Units. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 11, 169-171.
20. Матмусаева, М. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАСИ-МАКТАБГАЧА ЁШДАГИ БОЛАЛАР ИЖТИМОЙ ТАРБИЯ МАСКАНИ. ИЎДКОР О'ҚИТУВЧИ, 2(20), 130-132.
21. Matmusayeva, M. A., & Rustamova, N. A. (2021). DEVELOPING LOGICAL THINKING IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. Theoretical & Applied Science, (6), 658-660.

